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THE RELIANCE OF THE SUDANESE AUDIENCE ON SPECIALIZED SPORTS SATELLITE CHANNELS AS A SOURCE OF INFORMATION

A Survey Study within the Framework of Media Dependency Theory

Abdelnabi Abdalla Etaib

Professor of Journalism and New Media, Imam Muhammad ibn Saud Islamic University 2026

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Corresponding author: Abdelnabi Abdalla Etaib
(Email)

ABSTRACT

This study aimed to determine the degree of reliance of the Sudanese audience on specialized sports satellite channels and the relationship of this reliance with their sports interests. The study falls within the framework of descriptive studies and relied on the survey method. The study was conducted in the Berber locality in northern Sudan. Data was collected through an electronic questionnaire on Google Drive, which was distributed through WhatsApp groups covering all areas of the locality. The sample size was (450 individuals). The study reached a number of results, the most important of which are:

-The study revealed that the most watched specialized sports satellite channels among the sample individuals are the beIN Sports group, and specialized sports satellite channels came at the end of the list.

-The study showed that the vast majority of the sample individuals spend between (2-4 hours) watching specialized sports satellite channels.

-The study indicated that the Sudanese audience has been watching specialized sports satellite channels for a long time (more than five years).

-The study clarified that the most watched period of specialized sports satellite channels is the evening period (between dinner and midnight).

-The study found that the Sudanese audience has become accustomed to watching specialized sports satellite channels permanently, with the majority of the sample individuals.

-The study revealed that sports clubs are the preferred place for the Sudanese audience to watch specialized sports satellite channels.

-The study found that specialized sports satellite channels have greatly contributed to shaping the sports attitudes of the sample individuals.

-The study showed that the Sudanese audience is largely satisfied with the content provided by specialized sports satellite channels.

-The study detected that the strongest motivation for relying on specialized sports satellite channels is to stay up-to-date with the latest local and international sports news, followed by the motivation to follow the news of their favorite teams.

-The study clarified that the most preferred content among the sample individuals from watching specialized sports satellite channels is the live broadcast of matches.

-The study revealed that the sample individuals are affected by their exposure to specialized sports satellite channels cognitively, emotionally, and behaviorally.

-The study confirmed the complete satisfaction of the study sample with what is offered by specialized sports satellite channels.

The study recommends:

-Increasing attention to sports programs that address the interests of the Sudanese audience.

-Developing the sports content of specialized sports satellite channels to meet the needs of the Sudanese audience.

-Conducting future studies to follow up on changes in the reliance of the Sudanese audience on specialized sports satellite channels

1. INTRODUCTION TO THE STUDY

Specialized sports satellite channels have become a primary source for audiences to obtain sports information, as they provide comprehensive and live coverage of sports competitions and events. Sports channels in general are classified, according to the Arab States Broadcasting Union, within the category of knowledge-based channels, which include public, private, university (general diversified), and specialized channels. These channels provide serious content that responds to viewers' needs for knowledge, information, culture, education, and entertainment, and they comply with the professional standards of television production¹.

The importance of specialized sports channels lies in the fact that sports channels provide live coverage of sporting events, which allows audiences to follow matches and tournaments in real time. Sports channels also provide sports analyses presented by experts and analysts, which help audiences understand sporting events more deeply. In addition, sports channels provide additional information about teams and players, such as news, statements, and statistical analyses.

The reliance of audiences on specialized sports satellite channels in sports is attributed to the quality of coverage, as sports channels are characterized by providing high-quality coverage of sporting events through the use of advanced technologies such as live broadcasting and graphic visualization. Sports channels also provide a wide range of content, including matches, analytical programs, and sports news. Sports channels focus entirely on sports, which makes them a reliable source of sports information.

Sports channels contribute to increasing interest in sports, especially among young people. They also help enhance sports culture among audiences by providing sports-related information and analyses. In addition, sports channels can influence sports-related behavior by presenting positive role models and promoting sports values.

1.1. Best Practices for Sports Channels

Sports channels should provide high-quality content, with a focus on accuracy and objectivity. Specialized sports satellite channels provide comprehensive coverage of sporting events and offer in-depth sports analyses. Sports channels also interact with audiences through social media platforms and interactive programs, which increases audience engagement with these channels.

This study relied, in its theoretical framework, on Media Dependency Theory. Media Dependency

Theory explains that the ability of communication media to achieve greater cognitive, emotional, and behavioral effects increases when these media perform information transmission functions in a distinctive and intensive manner. The strength of this effect increases in cases of structural instability within society due to conflict and change. In addition, the idea of changing audience behavior, knowledge, and emotions can become a feedback effect that contributes to changes in both society and communication media. This represents the triangular relationship among communication media, the audience, and society².

1.2. Research Problem

Sport is considered one of the most important fields that attract public interest in Sudan, and sports satellite channels are among the most important media outlets that provide sports content to audiences. However, there is a lack of studies that examine the reliance of the Sudanese audience on sports satellite channels and its relationship with their sports interests. Therefore, this study aims to examine the reliance of the Sudanese audience on sports satellite channels and its relationship with their sports interests within the framework of Media Dependency Theory.

1.3. Research Questions

1. What is the degree of reliance of the Sudanese audience on sports satellite channels?
2. What are the sports interests of the Sudanese audience?
3. Is there a relationship between the reliance of the Sudanese audience on sports satellite channels and their sports interests?
4. How can this relationship be interpreted within the framework of Media Dependency Theory?

1.4. Research Objectives

1. To examine the reliance of the Sudanese audience on sports satellite channels.
2. To identify the sports interests of the Sudanese audience.
3. To analyze the relationship between the reliance of the Sudanese audience on sports satellite channels and their sports interests.
4. To interpret this relationship within the framework of Media Dependency Theory.

1.5. Significance of the Study

1. This study contributes to understanding the reliance of the Sudanese audience on sports satellite channels and its relationship with their sports interests.
2. This study may help in developing more

effective media strategies for sports satellite channels.

3. This study contributes to understanding the role of media in shaping the sports interests of audiences.

1.6. Previous Studies

The study conducted by **Nawar Al-Jabbara and Mohammed Al-Nadhari**³ aimed to identify the sports content discussed in the *Studio Al-Jamahir* program on Dijlah Satellite Channel, to determine the main themes presented by the program host, to identify the most important topics emphasized by the program's guests, and to identify the sports content that was not addressed through the program's reports.

The researchers used the analytical survey method and adopted a purposive sampling technique. Episodes of the *Studio Al-Jamahir* program broadcast on Dijlah Satellite Channel were selected during a one-month period, totaling (20) episodes.

Among the most prominent findings of the study was that issues related to training and coaches ranked first among the topics addressed by the program, while refereeing, referees, and the development of their performance ranked second among the program's areas of focus.

The study conducted by **Mohammed Bakri Al-Sheikh (2022)**⁴ aimed to examine the exposure of the Saudi university community to sports programs on Arab satellite channels for the purpose of watching sports activities. The researcher used the descriptive approach using the survey method. The study population consisted of faculty members, employees, and students at the College of Communication and Media at King Abdulaziz University in Jeddah, using a simple random sample. The sample size was (150) respondents, and data were collected through an electronic questionnaire.

The study revealed several findings, most notably that the age group most exposed to sports programs was youth aged (25 years and above). The **Qatari beIN Sports** channel ranked first among the sports channels followed by the study sample. The study also revealed that satellite channels constitute a primary source of sports culture for the Saudi audience included in the study sample.

The study conducted by **Al-Yousef (2022)**⁵ aimed to identify the rate of use of sports content by the Saudi audience through social media networks, specifically Twitter, to examine the motivations behind such use, the gratifications achieved, and the effects resulting from the audience's reliance on Twitter to follow sports content. The study also

examined the relationship between the use of sports content on Twitter and the general and personal mood state of the audience, the factors influencing this relationship, and how the Saudi audience manages its mood when receiving and being affected by sports content.

The study relied on the survey method by surveying a sample of (1,108) individuals from the Saudi audience, selected using the available (non-random) sampling method. Data were collected using an electronic questionnaire. The study reached several results, most notably that the average daily use of Twitter by the Saudi audience ranged from two to four hours. Approximately 94.3% of the Saudi audience follows sports content on Twitter either regularly or intermittently. News about favorite clubs ranked first among the sports content followed on Twitter, followed by match results and then news of local tournaments. Audience interaction with sports content on Twitter and satisfaction with that content were at a moderate level. Utilitarian motivations for exposure to sports content on Twitter ranked first, followed by ritualistic motivations. Content gratifications (guidance and social gratifications) were achieved at a high level, while communication process gratifications (quasi-guidance and quasi-social gratifications) were achieved at a moderate level. The results also showed that increased use of sports content on Twitter leads to increased cognitive, emotional, and behavioral effects among the audience.

The study conducted by **Shadia Mohammed Jaber (2022)**⁶ aimed to identify the relationship between sports programs on Egyptian satellite channels and the needs of children aged (9-12 years) in Port Said Governorate. The descriptive approach was used, and the research sample was selected using a purposive sampling method from children in late childhood enrolled in the fourth, fifth, and sixth grades in public primary schools during the academic year (2019-2020). The total sample size was (196) boys and girls, representing (13.9%) of the study population. The researcher designed a questionnaire as the data collection tool.

The study found that the overall relationship between the cognitive needs of children aged (9-12 years) and sports programs on Egyptian satellite channels achieved a relative importance of (56.77%) at a moderate level. The basic research sample agreed on the overall axis under study, which was attributed to the lack of consideration by those responsible for planning and producing sports programs on Egyptian satellite channels of the cognitive needs of children in this age group.

The study conducted by ****Mai Othman Salah El-Din et al. (2020)****⁷ aimed to identify the ethics of presenting sports programs on specialized satellite channels through the application to a sample of sports programs broadcast on specialized satellite channels, namely *Asdaa* Program and *Malab On Time* Program, during the period from March 2 to June 2020. This study falls within descriptive analytical studies and relied on the media survey method. The study reached several findings, most notably that there were differences in the commitment of sports program presenters in the study sample to presentation ethics according to the ownership pattern of the channel. The study also showed that presenters of sports programs on government-owned specialized satellite channels were more committed to ethical standards in their handling of various issues.

The study conducted by ****Iman Abdulrahman Al-Mashhadani (2020)****⁸ aimed to identify the extent of interest of university youth in following sports programs through television channels and to examine the level of exposure of the study sample to Iraqi satellite channels for the purpose of watching sports programs. The study population consisted of male and female students enrolled at the University of Baghdad during the academic year (2018–2019), with a sample size of (102) respondents. The researcher used a questionnaire as the main research tool for conducting the field study.

The study revealed several results, including that sports activities receive significant interest from university youth despite their academic and family commitments. The findings also showed that viewing rates were very high. Football ranked first among the sports activities followed by university youth. The study further indicated that sports programs increased youth awareness and sports-related knowledge and encouraged them to develop an interest in sports.

The study conducted by ****Nabil Khalil Nada et al. (2020)****⁹ aimed to identify the role of satellite channels in disseminating a culture of professionalism in wrestling within sports clubs from the perspectives of sports program presenters on specialized channels, members of the Egyptian Wrestling Federation, administrators of the Egyptian Wrestling Federation, coaches, administrators, and the wrestling audience. The study sample consisted of (130) respondents. The researchers used the descriptive survey method, and data were collected using a questionnaire.

The study highlighted several key findings, including the interest of the Egyptian Wrestling

Federation in inviting media outlets to follow its activities. The findings also indicated that sports programs contribute to strengthening the relationship between sports programs and wrestling institutions. In addition, specialized sports programs focusing on wrestling were found to be among the most widely followed sports programs by audiences.

The study conducted by **Ibrahim Masri and Alaa Ayash**¹⁰ aimed to identify youth reliance on satellite channels and their impact on the system of social values. The study population consisted of students from Gulf University and Palestine Ahliya University. The total sample size was (300) male and female students selected using a simple random sampling method. The study reached several findings, including that the highest percentage of youth watch satellite channels regularly. The MBC4 channel ranked first among the channels followed by youth, and youth showed a strong preference for watching these channels during the evening.

The study concluded with several recommendations, most notably the need to develop a strategy to reduce the viewing of television series that lead to moral decline, and the need to pay attention to media content and identify sources of risk that lead to changes in values.

The study conducted by ****Faisal Al-Mulla (2018)****¹¹ aimed to examine the role of sports satellite channels in spreading sports awareness among university youth in the Kingdom of Bahrain, to identify the most influential factors, and to clarify their impact on sports awareness. To achieve the study objectives, the researcher used the descriptive survey method and an electronic questionnaire to collect data. The sample size consisted of (250) students from Bahraini universities.

The results showed that watching sports satellite channels receives considerable attention among youth, which can be invested in spreading sports culture. The findings also indicated that watching satellite channels plays a positive role in spreading sports awareness among university youth in Bahrain. The results further revealed statistically significant differences in the respondents' assessments of the role of sports satellite channels in spreading sports awareness attributed to gender, university, and college type variables, while no statistically significant differences were attributed to the academic year variable. The study recommended the need to develop programs presented on satellite channels to contribute directly to enhancing sports awareness among youth.

The study conducted by **Khaled Al-Zyoud**¹²

aimed to identify the role of watching satellite channels in spreading sports culture among students at Yarmouk University. The researcher used a questionnaire consisting of (31) items distributed across four domains (cognitive, social, educational, and health). The sample size was (327) respondents from all university faculties except the Faculty of Physical Education. The results showed that sports satellite channels play a positive role in providing viewers with sports culture, with the social and cognitive domains ranking highest.

The study recommended paying greater attention to the quality of sports programs on satellite channels, particularly those that host experts, coaches, and referees, in order to increase the cultural value of these programs.

1.7. *Commentary on Previous Studies*

After reviewing the previous studies, the following can be concluded:

1. It was found that some studies related to the use of satellite channels addressed sports in its various branches, while other studies focused on the impact of general satellite channels.
2. At the theoretical level, most studies relied on Uses and Gratifications Theory and Media Dependency Theory, which is consistent with the theoretical framework of the present study.
3. At the methodological level, all studies fell within the framework of descriptive research, adopting the social survey method and using data collection tools that mainly relied on questionnaires and simple random sampling, which is consistent with this study

1.8. *Distinctive Features of the Present Study Compared to Previous Studies*

This study is distinguished from previous studies by selecting specialized sports channels as its field of investigation. These channels provide their services in the Arabic language.

1.9. *Ninth: Limits of the Study*

- **Subject-related limits:** The reliance of the Sudanese audience on specialized sports channels in sports content as a source of information.
- **Spatial limits:** Sudan – Berber locality. Berber was purposively selected as it represents a microcosm of Sudan that combines rural and urban characteristics, and due to the ease of data collection, as the researcher worked there for a long period.
- **Temporal limits:** The temporal limits of the field study cover a specific period during the year

2026.

1.10. *Tenth: Study Terminology*

1.10.1. *Reliance*

The researcher defines reliance as the extent to which media influence individuals' and communities' ideas, beliefs, and behaviors. Media reliance includes the use of information provided by media to shape public opinion and guide behavior.

1.10.2. *Specialized Sports Satellite Channels*

The researcher defines these as television or electronic channels that focus on broadcasting sports programs and sports-related media content. In this study, they include:

1.10.3. *Qatari Sports Channels*

- **beIN Sports:** A global network of encrypted sports channels providing comprehensive coverage of international sports events.
- **Al Kass Channels:** A network of free-to-air sports channels providing coverage of Qatari, Gulf, and international sports events.
- **Egyptian Sports Channels**
- **OnTime Sports:** A group of Egyptian sports channels providing coverage of Egyptian and international sports events.
- **Al Ahly Channel:** An Egyptian sports channel providing coverage of sports events related to Al Ahly Sporting Club.

1.10.4. *Saudi Sports Channels*

- **Saudi Sports Channels:** A group of Saudi sports channels providing coverage of Saudi and international sports events.
- **Channel 24 Sports:** A Saudi sports channel providing coverage of Saudi and international sports events, as well as Channel 8, which broadcasts the Saudi League.
- **Emirati Sports Channels**
- **Abu Dhabi Sports:** A group of Emirati sports channels providing coverage of Emirati and international sports events.
- **Dubai Sports:** An Emirati sports channel providing coverage of Emirati and international sports events.

These channels were selected based on the observation of viewers and followers of Arab sports channels.

1.10.5. *The Sudanese Audience*

The researcher defines the Sudanese audience as individuals from Sudanese society in Berber locality, northern Sudan, who follow specialized sports satellite channels.

2. METHODOLOGICAL PROCEDURES OF THE STUDY

2.1. First: Type and Method of the Study

This study falls within descriptive research, which focuses on describing social facts and phenomena and identifying their elements and components through collecting and interpreting information and data in order to present an accurate and objective picture of the phenomenon.

2.2. Second: Study Population and Sample

The study population includes Sudanese male and female audiences who are interested in and follow specialized sports channels.

Study Sample: The sample size reached (450) respondents. The sample was accessed through WhatsApp groups after designing the questionnaire on Google Drive and distributing the link to the groups.

2.3. Third: Data Collection Tools

The questionnaire was used as the primary tool for collecting data from an available sample of the Sudanese sports audience in Berber locality, northern Sudan.

1. **Demographic variables axis:** Included demographic factors (gender, age, educational level).
2. **Use and gratifications axis:** Included measuring the rate and motivations of audience use and exposure to specialized sports satellite channels.
3. **Reliance axis:** Included measuring the cognitive, emotional, and behavioral effects resulting from audience use of specialized sports channels.

2.4. Fifth: Validity and Reliability Testing

2.4.1. Validity Testing

Validity refers to the extent to which the scale accurately and precisely defines the concept it measures. Therefore, the scale should be free from systematic and random measurement errors. Validity begins with an accurate understanding of

the concepts to be measured, followed by precise formulation of their measures. The researcher verified the validity of the study instruments as follows:

a. Face Validity of the Study Instrument (Judges' Validity): To identify the face validity of the study instrument (questionnaire), the initial version was presented to a number of specialized judges in the field of the study. The number of judges was (3)³. The judges were asked to evaluate the scientific quality of the instrument in terms of its ability to measure what it was designed to measure, its suitability for the study objectives, the clarity of the statements, their relevance to the axis, and whether they measure the intended variables. They were also asked to suggest modifications, deletions, or additions. After reviewing the feedback and observations, the necessary amendments agreed upon by the majority of the judges were made, and the questionnaire was finalized.

b. Internal Consistency Validity: Internal consistency validity refers to the extent to which each questionnaire item is consistent with the domain to which it belongs. Internal consistency can be calculated by computing correlation coefficients between each item and the total score of its corresponding domain. A strong and statistically significant correlation coefficient indicates internal consistency validity. To verify internal consistency, Pearson's correlation coefficients were calculated between the scores of each item and the total score of the domain to which the item belongs.

2.4.2. Reliability Testing

The questionnaire was administered to a representative group of the sample. Reliability was verified by ensuring the stability of respondents' answers after administering the questionnaire to them twice.

3. GENERAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE STUDY SAMPLE

3.1. Gender

Table 1: Distribution of the Sample According to Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	390	86.6%
Female	60	13.3%
Total	450	100.0%

Based on the data presented in Table (1), it is evident that the majority of participants are males, accounting for 86.6%, compared to a low percentage of females at 13.3%. This can be attributed to the greater interest and participation of males in sports

activities compared to females, due to the conservative nature of society in the region

3.2. Age

Table 2: Distribution of the Sample According to Age

Age Group	Frequency	Percentage
Less than 20 years	18	4.0%

20-less than 30 years	170	37.8%
30-less than 40 years	109	24.2%
40-less than 50 years	74	16.4%
50-less than 60 years	69	15.3%
years and above 60	10	2.0%
Total	450	100.0%

Based on the data presented in Table (2), the age group (**20 to less than 30 years**) ranked first among the age groups participating in the study, with a percentage of **37.8%**. This was followed in second place by the age group (**30 to less than 40 years**) with a percentage of **24.2%**.

This indicates that the Sudanese audience relying on sports satellite channels is

predominantly composed of young people, particularly those within the age groups (**20 to less than 30 years**) and (**30 to less than 40 years**). These age groups are naturally more interested in sports due to the characteristics and tendencies of youth.

3.3. Marital Status

Table 3: Distribution of the Sample According to Marital Status

Marital Status	Frequency	Percentage
Married	375	83.3%
Single	50	11.1%
Widowed	5	1.1%
Divorced	20	4.4%
Total	450	100.0%

Based on the results shown in Table (3), it is observed that the **married** category ranked first among the different marital status categories, accounting for **83%** of the sample, which represents more than three-quarters of the total

sample. This finding is consistent with the results of Table (2) and indicates that early marriage is a common practice in Sudanese rural society.

3.4. Educational Level

Table 4: Distribution of the Sample According to Educational Level

Educational Level	Frequency	Percentage
Less than 20 years	10	2.2%
20-less than 30 years	192	42.2%
30-less than 40 years	58	12.9%
40-less than 50 years	155	28.7%
50-less than 60 years	25	5.5%
years and above 60	10	2.2%
Total	450	100.0%

The results of Table (4) indicate that the majority of the sample falls within the category of individuals holding a **secondary education certificate**, accounting for **42.2%**. This is followed in second place by individuals holding a **bachelor's degree**, who represent **28.7%** of the sample.

This reflects that the Sudanese audience relying on sports satellite channels belongs largely to the educated segment of society, which highlights the importance of specialized sports channels among the Sudanese audience.

3.5. Occupation

Table 5: Distribution of the Sample According to Occupational Status

Occupational Status	Frequency	Percentage
Government employee	112	24.9%
Military personnel	23	5.1%
Private sector employee	100	22.2%
Charity sector employee	12	2.6%
Student	120	26.6%
Self-employed	60	13.3%
Unemployed	23	5.1%
Total	450	100.0%

The data presented in Table (5) indicate that the **student** category recorded the highest participation rate among the various occupational categories, with a percentage of **26.6%**. This was followed in second place by **government employees**, who accounted for **24.9%** of the participants.

This finding is consistent with the results of Table (4) and indicates that educated audiences are the most interested in relying on sports satellite channels

3.6. Sports Channels Followed by the Audience

Table 6: Distribution of the Sample According to the Sports Channels Followed

Channel	Frequency	Percentage
Al Jazeera Sports Channels Group	208	46.2%
Egyptian Sports Channels Group	50	11.0%
Saudi Sports Channels Group	59	13.1%
Emirati Sports Channels Group	50	11.0%
Sudanese Sports Channels Group	40	8.0%
Other channels	93	20.6%
Total (sample)	540	100.0%

Based on the data presented in Table (6), it is evident that nearly half of the study sample, at a rate of **46.2%**, follow **Al Jazeera Sports channels**. This is attributed to Al Jazeera's monopoly over the broadcasting rights of most major sports tournaments. The category of respondents who follow sports through **other channels** ranked second.

In contrast, the percentage of respondents who follow **Sudanese sports channels** was notably low, reaching only **8%**. The researcher attributes this decline to the suspension of Sudanese satellite channels due to the war and the long-term halt of sports activities in Sudan

3.7. Level of Respondents' Exposure to Specialized Sports Channels

Table 7: Rate of Respondents' Exposure to Specialized Sports Channels

Daily Viewing Rate	Frequency	Percentage
Less than one hour	54	12.0%
One hour - less than two hours	50	11.0%
Two hours - less than four hours	297	66.0%
Four hours or more	50	11.0%
Total	450	100.0%

The data in Table (7) indicate that the highest rate of Sudanese audience exposure to specialized sports satellite channels was for viewing periods ranging **from two to four hours**, ranking first with a percentage of **66%**. This indicates that the vast

majority of the sample follow specialized sports channels during this time period, which corresponds with the scheduled broadcast times of sports matches and audiences' leisure time

Table 8: Duration of Respondents' Use of Sports Satellite Channels

Duration of Use	Frequency	Percentage
Less than one hour	40	8.8%
One hour - less than three hours	87	19.3%
Three hours - less than five hours	118	26.2%
Five hours or more	200	44.4%
Total	450	100.0%

The data presented in Table (8) indicate that the majority of the Sudanese respondents in the study sample have been using sports satellite channels for **more than five years**. This represents an

important indicator of reliance on sports satellite channels and also reflects the role of these channels in satisfying the respondents' sports interests.

Table 9: Preferred Daily Time Periods for Following Sports Content on Specialized Sports Satellite Channels

Preferred Time Period	Frequency	Percentage
From dawn to noon	15	3.3%
From noon to afternoon	26	5.7%
From afternoon to sunset	28	6.2%
From sunset to dinner	36	8.0%
From dinner to midnight	258	57.3%
From midnight to dawn	63	14.0%
No specific time period	51	11.3%
Total	450	100.0%

The results of Table (9) indicate that **more than half of the Sudanese respondents** follow sports satellite channels during the period **from dinner until midnight**, with a percentage of **61.6%**. The researcher attributes this to the fact that most matches and related sports programs are

broadcast during this time period. This finding is consistent with the results of Table (7) and indicates that the Sudanese audience follows specialized sports satellite channels extensively, reflecting a high level of reliance on them

Table 10: Respondents' Follow-up of Sports Satellite Channels

Level of Follow-up	Frequency	Percentage
Always follow	305	57.9%

Follow to some extent	112	36.4%
Do not follow	33	5.7%
Total	450	100.0%

The results of Table (10) indicate that more than half of the study sample, at a rate of **57.9%**, **always** follow sports satellite channels, while **36.4%** follow sports satellite channels **occasionally**. In contrast, a very small percentage, **5.7%**, do not follow sports content through sports satellite channels.

Based on the two categories (**always** and **occasionally**), it is evident that the majority of the

Table 11: Preferred Places for Respondents to Follow Sports Satellite Channels

Preferred Place	Frequency	Percentage
Home	112	24.9%
Club	205	45.5%
With neighbors and friends	112	24.9%
No specific place	21	4.7%
Total sample	450	100.0%

The results of Table (11) indicate that **sports clubs** ranked first among the places preferred by the study sample for following specialized sports satellite channels. According to the researcher's observation, this is attributed to the fact that sports clubs receive significant interest from residents of the area and are well equipped in terms of space and viewing facilities, which makes them a

Table 12: Extent to Which Specialized Sports Satellite Channels Contribute to Shaping Respondents' Attitudes Toward Sports Issues

Degree of Contribution	Frequency	Percentage
Contributed to a large extent	261	58.0%
Contributed to some extent	123	27.3%
Did not contribute	66	14.7%
Total	450	100.0%

The results of Table (12) indicate that more than half of the study sample, at a rate of **58%**, believe that specialized sports satellite channels have contributed **to a large extent** to shaping attitudes toward sports issues. Meanwhile, **27.3%** of respondents believe that specialized sports

Table 13: Level of Respondents' Satisfaction with the Sports Content Provided by Specialized Sports Satellite Channels

Level of Satisfaction	Frequency	Percentage
Highly satisfied	219	48.7%
Satisfied	120	26.7%
Satisfied to some extent	80	17.8%
Not satisfied	31	6.8%
Not satisfied at all	0	0.0%
Total	450	100.0%

The results of Table (13) show that the largest proportion of the study sample is **highly satisfied** with the content provided by specialized sports satellite channels, with a percentage of **48.7%**, while **26.7%** of respondents reported being

Table 15: Motivations for Exposure to Specialized Sports Channels (Respondents were asked to select the most preferred motivations)

Motivation for Exposure	Frequency	Percentage
Following the latest local and international sports news	219	48.7%
Following news of favorite clubs	120	26.7%
Developing my knowledge of sports topics	80	17.8%

Sudanese audience relies heavily on following sports issues through sports satellite channels. This finding is consistent with the results of Tables (7) and (9), indicating a high level of reliance on specialized sports satellite channel.

3.8. Respondents' Viewing Habits of Sports Satellite Channels

preferred location for following sports satellite channels. In addition, sports clubs provide an atmosphere that encourages discussion, which is consistent with the interactive nature of sports

3.9. Contribution of Sports Satellite Channels to Shaping Attitudes Toward Sports Issues

satellite channels have contributed **to some extent** to shaping attitudes toward sports issues. This indicates that the Sudanese audience relies on these channels in following and understanding sports issues.

satisfied. This indicates that the level of audience satisfaction with the sports content provided by specialized sports satellite channels is **very high**, which reinforces the results of Table (12).

Entertainment	31	6.8%
Habit and filling free time	0	0.0%
Total	450	100.0%

The results of Table (15) indicate that the **strongest motivation** for exposure to specialized sports satellite channels is **following the latest local and international sports news**, with a high percentage of **48.7%**, which reflects the study sample's reliance on specialized sports satellite

channels. This is followed by **following news of favorite clubs** at a rate of **26.7%**. This indicates that specialized sports satellite channels constitute the primary source of sports news for the Sudanese audience.

Table 16: Types of Sports Content Most Followed by Respondents on Sports Channels
(Respondents were asked to select the most preferred content)

Content Type	Frequency	Percentage
Live match broadcasts	309	68.7%
Local tournaments news	19	4.2%
Arab tournaments news	20	4.4%
Continental tournaments news	12	2.6%
International tournaments news	90	20.0%
Total	450	100.0%

Reliance on specialized sports satellite channels for **broadcasting matches and competitions** ranked first among the types of content followed by the study sample, with a large majority reaching **68.7%**. According to the researcher's assessment, this is attributed to the nature of these channels and the content they provide, which

focuses primarily on broadcasting matches from international leagues and major tournaments.

It is also noted that **news of international tournaments** ranked second, which confirms the strong reliance of the Sudanese audience on specialized sports satellite channels

Table 17: Effects of Reliance on Specialized Sports Satellite Channels
(Respondents were asked to select the most preferred effect)

Effect	Frequency	Percentage
Increased my knowledge of local and international sports events	45	10.0%
Contributed to shaping my opinions and convictions about sports issues	50	11.1%
Expanded my understanding of what is happening in the sports arena	60	13.3%
Made me feel a sense of belonging to sports in my country	45	10.0%
More than one effect	250	55.6%
Total	450	100.0%

The category **"more than one effect"** ranked first among the types of effects, with a percentage of **55.6%**. The remaining values of the effects were relatively close, which reveals the strength of reliance on specialized sports satellite channels in

increasing knowledge, shaping convictions, expanding understanding, and enhancing sports affiliation. This indicates that the impact of specialized sports channels encompasses **all types of effects: cognitive, behavioral, and emotional**.

Table 18: General Satisfaction with the Content Provided by Sports Satellite Channels

Level of Satisfaction	Frequency	Percentage
Very satisfied	321	71.3%
Satisfied	100	22.2%
Satisfied to some extent	29	6.5%
Not satisfied	0	0.0%
Not satisfied at all	0	0.0%
Total	450	100.0%

Table (18) shows that specialized sports satellite channels have achieved satisfaction at all levels. The category **"very satisfied"** ranked first with a percentage of **71.3%**, followed by **"satisfied"** in second place with **22.2%**, while **"satisfied to some extent"** ranked third with a low percentage of **6.5%**.

This indicates that all members of the study sample are satisfied with the content provided by specialized sports satellite channels, which confirms the reliance of the Sudanese audience on these channels

4. RESULTS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the presentation and interpretation of the study tables, the following results were obtained:

1. The study showed that **male youth** are the most frequent followers of specialized sports satellite channels.
2. The study confirmed that the age group **(20 to less than 30 years)** represents the category most engaged in following specialized sports satellite channels.

3. The study indicated that the vast majority of followers of specialized sports satellite channels belong to the **married** category.
4. The study revealed that most followers of specialized sports satellite channels are from the **educated groups** (secondary school and university graduates).
5. The study showed that the majority of followers of specialized sports satellite channels are **students and government employees**.
6. The study revealed that the most followed specialized sports satellite channels among the study sample are the **beIN Sports network**, while Sudanese specialized sports channels ranked last.
7. The study indicated that the vast majority of the sample spend **between two and four hours** watching specialized sports satellite channels.
8. The study showed that the Sudanese audience has been following specialized sports satellite channels for a long period (**more than five years**).
9. The study indicated that the most preferred time period for following specialized sports satellite channels is the **evening period (between dinner and midnight)**.
10. The study concluded that the Sudanese audience has become accustomed to regularly following specialized sports satellite channels, as reported by the majority of the sample.
11. The study revealed that **sports clubs** are the preferred places for the Sudanese audience to follow specialized sports satellite channels.
12. The study concluded that specialized sports satellite channels have contributed significantly to shaping the **sports attitudes** of the study sample.
13. The study showed that the Sudanese audience is **highly satisfied** with the content provided by specialized sports satellite channels.
14. The study observed that the strongest motivation for relying on specialized sports satellite channels is **following the latest local and international sports news**, followed by the motivation of following news of favorite clubs.
15. The study indicated that the most preferred content among the study sample when following specialized sports satellite channels is **live match broadcasting**.
16. The study revealed that the study sample is affected **cognitively, emotionally, and behaviorally** by their exposure to specialized sports satellite channels.
17. The study confirmed the **complete satisfaction** of the study sample with what is provided by specialized sports satellite channels.

5. RECOMMENDATIONS

The study recommends the following:

- Increasing attention to sports programs that address the interests of the Sudanese audience.
- Developing sports content on specialized sports channels to meet the needs of the Sudanese audience.
- Conducting future studies to monitor changes in the Sudanese audience's reliance on specialized sports channels.

6. STUDY LIMITATIONS

- The study was limited to the Sudanese audience.
- The social survey method was used.

CONTRIBUTION OF THE STUDY

- Providing information about the reliance of the Sudanese audience on specialized sports channels.
- Contributing to the development of sports content on specialized sports channels.

REFERENCES

1. Mohammed Shattah, *Encrypted Television Channels and Sports Programs: A Field Study of the Sports Audience in the University Environment*.
2. Yusuf Kafi, *Public Opinion and Communication Theories*, 2015, First Edition, Dar Al-Hamed for Publishing and Distribution, Amman, Jordan.
3. Nawar Mohammed Abdullah Al-Jabbara & Mohammed Hussein Al-Nadhari, *Sports Program Content on Iraqi Satellite Channels: An Analytical Study of the Studio Al-Jamahir Program*, Al-Bayda University Journal, Vol. 7, No. 1, 2025.
4. Mohammed Bakri Al-Sheikh, *Gratifications Achieved from the Exposure of the Saudi University Community to Sports Programs on Arab Satellite Channels*, Al-Hikma Journal for Media Studies, Khartoum, 2022.
5. Abdulaziz bin Ali bin Abdulrahman Al-Yousef, *The Use of Sports Content by the Saudi Audience through Social Media Networks and Its Relationship with Mood State*, Unpublished Doctoral Dissertation, Imam Muhammad ibn Saud Islamic University, Riyadh, 2022.

6. Shadia Mohammed Jaber Hassanein, *Educational Dimensions in Talk Shows Presented on Egyptian Satellite Channels*, *Childhood Studies Journal*, Ain Shams University, Vol. 23, No. 86, 2020.
7. Mai Othman Salah El-Din et al., *Ethics of Presenting Sports Programs on Specialized Satellite Channels: An Analytical Study*, *Scientific Journal of the Faculty of Arts*, Assiut University, 2020.
8. Iman Abdulrahman Al-Mashhadani, *The Role of Iraqi Satellite Channels in Developing Sports Culture among Youth: A Field Study*, *Egyptian Journal of Media Research*, Issue 60, 2020.
9. Nabil Khaled Nada, Mohammed Ahmed Mansour, & Khaled Abdelnabi Hassanein, *The Role of Satellite Channels in Spreading a Culture of Professionalism in Wrestling within Sports Clubs*, *Journal of the Faculty of Physical Education and Sports Sciences*, Vol. 26, No. 11, 2020.
10. Ibrahim Suleiman Masri & Alaa Mohammed Ayash, *Youth Reliance on Satellite Channels and Its Impact on the System of Social Values*, *Algerian Journal of Social and Human Sciences*, Vol. 7, No. 2, 2019.
11. Faisal Hamid Al-Mulla, *The Role of Sports Satellite Channels in Spreading Sports Awareness among University Youth in the Kingdom of Bahrain*, *Journal of Gulf and Arabian Peninsula Studies*, University of Bahrain, 2018.
12. Khaled Mahmoud Al-Zyoud, *The Role of Watching Sports Satellite Channels in Spreading Sports Culture among Yarmouk University Students*, *Islamic University Journal of Educational and Psychological Studies*, Vol. 21, No. 4, 2013.
13. Reviewers: Dr. Al-Nourani Al-Bashir Mohammed Al-Hassan (Imam Muhammad ibn Saud Islamic University); Prof. Mortada Al-Bashir Othman (King Khalid University); Dr. Badr Al-Din Mohammed Farah (Director of News, Nile River Satellite Channel).